

THE USE OF GERMAN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS ABOUT VALUES AND ANTI-VALUES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS AT UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

The values, national-cultural traditions and peculiarities of worldview are most clearly manifested in phraseological units, therefore the phraseological fund of a language seems to be one of the most interesting and productive objects of research in the axiological sphere. The meanings of phraseological units reflect value judgments and behavioral stereotypes of representatives of a particular culture. Values, as an integral part of the linguistic personality, are the most fundamental characteristics of culture, the highest guidelines for behavior.

The article analyzes German axiological phraseological units that reflect national values and anti-values; the effectiveness of their use in the process of teaching a foreign language is substantiated.

The relevance of the study is due to the fact that the formation of a value system for future specialists is an obligatory component of the educational process at university.

The purpose of the study is to determine the basic values and anti-values contained in German axiological phraseological units.

The article emphasizes that familiarizing students with axiological phraseology in the linguocultural aspect and the peculiarities of the national mentality will allow the formation of true human values that are a priority.

As a result of the study, it was determined that in foreign language classes at university it is advisable to analyze the axiological meaning of phraseological units, primarily proverbs, sayings, aphorisms of dyads: "Life - Death", "Work - Rest. Laziness. Idleness", "Truth - Lie", "Wealth - Poverty", "Homeland - Foreign Land". The phraseologisms of the above-mentioned dyads include such important aspects as: lifestyle; attitude towards your own and other people's lives; relationship between people; spiritual and non-spiritual life; attitude towards work; perception of truth and lies; patriotism.

Purposeful work on phraseological units that represent values and anti-values in foreign language lesson at university will help the correct formation of the student's personality and understanding of the national character of representatives of the country of target language.

Keywords: university, student, foreign language teaching, values, anti-values, axiological phraseological unit, national character.

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, in connection with the global spiritual and value crisis that humanity is experiencing at the turn of eras, axiological research is becoming especially relevant. Initially, axiology emerged as a discipline that defined the very concept of “value”, the most important of the categories of the spiritual world, and designated the priority of spiritual values for man as a being who creates the world of culture and creatively realizes himself in it as an individual.

The problem of values is no longer just a philosophical category. Increasingly, values are becoming the object of close attention and interest of linguists. Issues of axiological understanding of value are considered in inextricable connection with the linguistic expression of value and evaluation, since the most effective and widespread way of transmitting information, the content of which is the qualification of phenomena of nature, society and thinking, is the language system.

The cumulative function of language, in which language acts as a repository and means of transmitting extra-linguistic collective experience, is most clearly manifested in the field of phraseology. Phraseological material records the peculiarities of the natural and geographical conditions of the country, its history, economy, politics, culture, way of life, and customs of the people, therefore the close connection of phraseology with various spheres of human activity is noticeable.

The analysis of phraseological units in the axiological aspect in foreign language classes is of great educational importance, since it contributes to the formation of a value system for future specialists (Andreeva, Korneva, Kapustina, 2018; Andreyeva, Nazmieva, Sakhbullina, 2018; Andreeva, Korneva, Chugunov, 2022; Andreeva, Korneva, Kapustina, & Andreev, 2024).

2. DISCUSSION

The values, as an integral part of the linguistic personality, are the most fundamental characteristics of culture, the highest guidelines for behavior. According to P.S. Gurevich, these guidelines arise not only on the basis of knowledge and information, but also a person's own life experience; they represent a personally colored attitude towards the world (Gurevich, 1995, p.120).

The linguistic classification of values takes into account the axiological side of the problem. The values are largely determined by ideology, social institutions, beliefs, and needs. For a comprehensive understanding of values in language, one should consider the model of the value picture of the world, which, along with the linguistic picture of the world, is objectively highlighted in the language. The value picture of the world reflects ethnocultural and sociocultural plans in relation to various types of evaluative relations (Toporova, 1994).

When analyzing and describing the value picture of the world in language, researchers propose to take into account the following provisions:

- 1) the value picture of the world in language contains universal and specific parts;
- 2) the value picture of the world in language is reconstructed in the form of interconnected value judgments that correlate with legal, moral, religious codes, generally accepted judgments of common sense, as well as with typical folklore stories;
- 3) the value picture of the world presents the most important meanings for a particular culture, value dominants, the totality of which forms a certain type of culture, which is supported and preserved in language;
- 4) within the framework of one linguistic culture, the value picture of the world is a heterogeneous formation, since different social or age groups may have different values;
- 5) the value picture of the world exists in both individual and collective consciousness (Karasik, 2002).

N.D. Arutyunova notes that the value picture of the world of society includes a certain set and hierarchy of values expressed in assessments (Arutyunova, 1988). The evaluation process consists in the subject's awareness of the value of the object, which is embodied in the form of a judgment to the value that has

become the subject of evaluation (Prishchepchuk, 2008). The assessment is based on the principle of anthropometricity - the comparison of entities in accordance with human knowledge and ideas, as well as with the system of national and cultural stereotypes.

The value picture of the world is one of the aspects of the worldview; it is defined as a characteristic of a system of ideals that set the idea of what the world around us should be like. The reconstruction of the value picture of the world can occur through interrelated value judgments, as well as with the help of individual associates. The value picture of the world presents the most important meanings for national culture.

The researcher V.I. Karasik describes the concept of a linguistic picture of the world, highlighting various evaluative relations as linguistic values, for example, attitudes towards elders and younger, children, women and men, animals, property, health and illness, death, competitions and games, to work and feat, to miracles and everyday life, to privacy, to housing, to earth and sky, to natural phenomena, to time and space (Karasik, 2002).

3. RESULTS

In foreign language classes at a university, it is advisable to analyze the axiological meaning of phraseological units, primarily proverbs, sayings, aphorisms of dyads: "Life - Death", "Work - Rest. Laziness. Idleness", "Truth - Lie", "Wealth - Poverty", "Homeland - Foreign Land" (according to the classification of L.K. Bayramova) (Bayramova, 2008). Phraseologisms of the above-mentioned dyads include such important aspects as: lifestyle; attitude towards your own and other people's lives; relationship between people; spiritual and non-spiritual life; attitude towards work; perception of truth and lies; patriotism.

Proverbs, sayings, and aphorisms containing morality are value-oriented and in their totality form a value-based picture of the world (Bayramova, 2008).

The value "Labor" is reflected in German proverbs and aphorisms: *Ohne Fleiß kein Preis* (Without labor there is no result); *Von einem Streiche fällt keine Eiche* (An oak tree does not fall from one blow); *Wer den Kern essen will, muss die Schale knacken* (Whoever wants to eat grain must crack the shell); *Geduld und Fleiß bricht Eis* (Patience and work break the ice); *Arbeit ist des Bürgers Zierde* (F. Schiller. "Das Lied von der Glocke") (Labor makes a man). The moral of the above phraseological units is this: to achieve something, you need to work hard; hard work produces results; a person finds self-expression in work.

The anti-value "Laziness" is recorded in the following phraseological units: *Ehrlichkeit und Faulheit können niemals Freunde werden* (Esther Klepgen, 1965) (Honesty and laziness can never become friends); *Müßiggang ist aller Laster Anfang* (Idleness is the beginning of all vice); *Nichtstun ist die Mutter aller Missetaten* (Napoleon I. Bonaparte) (Idleness is the mother of all atrocities); *Rast' ich, so rast' ich* (I rest, so I rust); *Faulheit geht so langsam, daß Armut sie überholt.* (Aus Holland) (Laziness moves so slowly that poverty outstrips it). The moral of the listed proverbs and aphorisms can be expressed in the following statements: laziness is detrimental to a person; laziness leads to poverty.

The way of life of the Germans, like other peoples, emphasizes the value "Time". The perception of time is characterized by strict planning and strict adherence to the plan, a high pace of life: *Zeit ist Geld* - Time is money; *Zeit und Stunde warten nicht* (Time doesn't wait); *Morgen, morgen, nur nicht heute, sagen alle faulen Leute* (Tomorrow, tomorrow, but not today - that's what all lazy people say); *Was du heute kannst besorgen, das verschiebe nie auf morgen* (Never put off until tomorrow what you can do today); *des Faulen Werktag ist immer morgen, sein Ruhetag heute* (lit. A lazy person's working day is always tomorrow, and his day off is today); *Aufschub ist ein Tagesdieb* (lit. putting off steals the day); *Wer kommt nicht zur rechten Zeit, der muß essen, was übrigbleibt* (lit., whoever doesn't arrive on time has to eat what's left). The above phraseological units contain a moral: time must be valued, it is as valuable as money; you should not put off your business; everything needs to be done on time.

The value "Order" is idealized in the German way of life, as evidenced by phraseological units: *Ordnung ist das halbe Leben* (lit. Order is half of life); *Heilige Ordnung, segensreiche Himmelstochter* - Holy order - blessed son of heaven (F. Schiller); *auf strenge Zucht halten* (maintain strict order); *j-d kommt mit dem Glockenschlag* (smb. comes strictly on the clock, minute by minute).

The complete consistency of the Germans in carrying out orders and instructions or in implementing their principles is reflected in the aphorism: *Deutsch sein heißt, eine Sache um ihrer selbst willen treiben* (lit. to be a German is to do a thing for its own sake). This catchphrase comes from Richard Wagner's "Deutsche

Kunst und deutsche Politik”.

The values “Forethought”, “Caution” are recorded in the following phraseological units: *Kleine Löchlein machen das Schiff voll Wasser* (lit. Small holes can cause a ship to sink); *Aus einem Funken wird oft das große Feuer* (lit. A spark often causes a great fire); *Ein Funken noch so klein, äschert ganze Städte ein* (lit. Such a small spark turns a city into ashes); *Geringe Ursache, große Wirkung* (lit. Small cause - great consequences); *Vorsicht schadet nicht* (lit. Caution does not harm); *Vorsicht ist die Mutter der Weisheit* (lit. Foresight is the mother of wisdom); *Erst wägen, dann wagen* (lit. First weigh everything, then decide); *Erst bestimmen, dann beginnen* (lit. First think about it, then start); *Besser zweimal messen, als einmal vergessen* (lit. It is better to measure twice than to forget once). The above proverbs contain a moral: you need to take responsibility for your actions; you always need to think about the consequences of a particular action.

The values “Thrift” and “Practicality” are reflected in proverbs with various names of monetary units, reflecting the thrifty attitude of the Germans towards money: *Aus Kreuzern werden Gulden* (lit. From the Kreuzers come guilders); *Aus Pfennigen werden Taler* (lit. Thalers come from Pfennigs); *Drei Heller sind auch Geld* (lit. Three hellers is also money); *Ein Groschen zum andern wird mit der Zeit ein Schatz* (lit. From pennies a fortune grows over time); *Es ist ein guter Batzen, der einen Gulden erspart* (lit. Good is the batzen who protects the guilder); *Heller zu Heller, so wird ein Gulden draus* (lit. From the hellers comes the guilder); *Meine Kreuzer sind auch Geld* (lit. My kreuzers is also money); *Viel Kreuzer machen einen Gulden* (lit. From several kreuzers a guilder emerges); *Wer einen Groschen spart, hat zwei verdient* (lit. He who saves a penny deserves two pennies).

The anti-value “Wastefulness” is presented in proverbs: *Wer den Heller nicht ehrt, ist des Talers nicht wert* (lit. He who does not honor the heller is not worthy of a thaler); *Wer den Pfennig nicht ehrt, ist des Talers nicht wert* (lit. He who does not honor Pfennig is not worthy of a thaler); *Wer den Pfennig nicht spart, kommt nicht zum Groschen* (lit. He who does not save a pfennig will not receive a penny).

The moral of the above phraseological units lies in the statements: frugality and the ability to save make small money big; you need to spend money wisely.

The value of “Practicality” is manifested in all spheres of German life, which is reflected in phraseological units: *Der kluge man baut vor* (lit. A smart person makes a stock); *Mit Dank schmelzt man keine Suppe* (lit. You can't put thanks in the soup); *“Hab’ Dank” füllt den Beutel nicht* (lit. Gratitude will not fill the wallet); *Was nutzt mir ein Lob, wenn ich hab kein Brot* (lit. Why do I need praise if I don't have bread). For Germans, the ability to save means the ability to live correctly, wisely and is an important virtue. E. Bovkun notes: “The Germans save everything: money, working time, natural and energy resources... Thrift has become not just a tradition, but a public duty, an obligation to protect natural resources and the environment to a greater extent than material wealth” (Cit. from: (Maltseva, 2001, p. 374)).

Thus, the meanings of phraseological units reflect value judgments and behavioral stereotypes of representatives of a particular culture, since “the value picture of the world in a language is a manifestation of the semantic law, according to which the most important objects and phenomena of the life of the people receive a varied and detailed nomination” (Karasik, 2002, p. 205).

To effectively teach axiological phraseology in foreign language classes at university, certain conditions should be taken into account:

- 1) Phraseological units about values and anti-values should be present throughout the entire educational process as students master lexical and grammatical material.
- 2) The study of phraseological units should be based on understanding of the semantics of a phraseological unit and its axiological meaning.
- 3) The development of a set of exercises should be aimed at developing the skills and abilities of perception, understanding and use of phraseological units in the language.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Purposeful work on phraseological units that represent values and anti-values in foreign language classes at university will help the correct formation of the student's personality, understanding the characteristics of the national character of representatives of the country of the language being studied by university graduates.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work is performed according to the Russian Government Program of Competitive Growth of Kazan Federal University.

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